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Press Hardening for Sustainable Lightweight Chassis Design in Heavy-Duty Vehicles: A Material Performance and Life Cycle Assessment Approach

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ABSTRACT

The transport sector is critical for reducing GHG emissions. Heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs) remain challenging due to slow electrification and rising demand. Lightweighting using advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) and press-hardened boron steels offers a practical solution. These materials combine strength, fatigue resistance, cost efficiency, and lower environmental impact compared to other lightweighting alternatives. This work assesses the effectiveness of different steels and manufacturing processes for lightweighting HDV chassis components, focusing on fatigue performance and life cycle environmental impacts. Comparing cold stamped hot rolled AHSS with press hardened 22MnB5 sheets shows that press hardening can cut weight by up to 34% without compromising fatigue resistance, especially when paired with shot peening. Cradle-to-grave LCAs across BEV, HEV, and PHEV configurations reveal that the use phase dominates impacts (88%–99%). Press-hardened components reduce global warming potential and resource depletion by 21%–32%, particularly in HEV and PHEV scenarios. These findings underscore the role of strategic lightweighting and material selection in supporting transport sector climate goals.

1 | Introduction

1.1 | Lightweight in Heavy-Duty Vehicles

The transportation sector plays a crucial role in achieving ambitious climate goals [1, 2]. Currently, transportation accounts for about 32% of greenhouse gas emissions, with road transport being the main contributor at 73%. Beyond electrification, one of the most significant strategies is reducing vehicle weight. This approach supports the principles of a circular economy

and sustainable resource management, aiming for a carbon-neutral system with zero emissions in the coming decades [3]. Many actions have been taken to cut GHG emissions from road transportation. However, as emissions from passenger cars decrease, those from heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs) and buses are not expected to fall at the same rate. This is due to challenges in electrifying these vehicles and the projected increase in their use by 2050. Truck activity is expected to rise by 44% and bus activity by 72% [4]. To address this, the European Commission

Abbreviations: σ^{100k} , Fatigue strength at 100 000 cycles; AHSS, Advanced high-strength steels; BEV, Battery electric vehicle; BiW, Body-in-white; CFRP, Carbon fiber reinforced polymers; CML, Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden (LCA method); EV, Electric vehicle; EoL, End-of-Life; GHG, Greenhouse gas; HDV, Heavy-duty vehicle; HEV, Hybrid electric vehicle; HSLA, High strength low alloyed; ICEV, Internal combustion engine vehicle; LCA, Life cycle assessment; PHEV, Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle; UTS, Ultimate tensile strength; YS, Yield strength.

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has proposed legislation requiring the average emissions of HDVs to be reduced by 90% by 2040 compared to 2019 levels.

In recent years, lightweighting efforts have focused mainly on passenger cars. Among many materials, advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) and press-hardened boron steels have become popular choices to optimize the light design. These materials offer an optimal balance of mechanical strength and cost-effectiveness for structural components. As a result, they have been widely used for over a decade in various automotive parts, especially in the body-in-white (BiW) and closures, achieving weight savings of about 25%–35% using cold-rolled sheets. BiW parts have focused most of the weight optimization actions, while improving crash resistance.

Chassis parts represent about 20%–25% of the vehicle weight, similar to the BiW. Therefore, lightweighting the chassis could lead to significant overall mass savings. Unlike BiW parts, where crashworthiness and strength are the relevant properties, chassis parts have to meet strict fatigue requirements. This limits the use of some lightweight solutions developed for BiW. Aluminum alloys are not suitable for chassis parts because they lack sufficient stiffness and fatigue resistance. Steels and carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) are better candidates [5–10]. The current costs, recyclability, and manufacturing productivity of CFRP parts cannot compete with steel in high volume vehicle production. In addition, steel parts show the lowest environmental impact regarding raw material extraction and manufacturing, compared to aluminum alloys or CFRP. In terms of CO₂ footprint, the introduction of steel grades with higher strength, such as the AHSS family, does not significantly increase the environmental impact of the material itself, as opposed to the current CFRP. Therefore, cold forming of AHSS and press hardening of B steels are the most realistic solutions for reducing chassis weight while improving durability, keeping costs, and environmental impact low.

Lightweighting trucks reduces GHG emissions differently than in passenger cars, where weight savings reduce fuel consumption. For trucks, weight savings allow for a higher maximum payload without increasing the gross vehicle weight. This means that

fewer trips are needed to transport the same amount of goods, improving transport efficiency. For example, a 10% reduction in truck weight results in a 10% increase in transport efficiency for weight-limited transport. This is illustrated in Figure 1.

1.2 | Selection of Steel Grades for Chassis Parts in Heavy-Duty Vehicles

HDVs offer opportunities for weight reduction in both the cabin and chassis, which together constitute 60%–70% of the curb weight [11]. Cabin parts are manufactured from cold-rolled sheets (1–3 mm), similar to the BiW components in passenger cars. Consequently, advances in materials for passenger cars can also help to reduce the weight of cabin parts. However, HDV chassis require high stiffness and fatigue resistance, necessitating the use of thick, hot-rolled sheets (6–10 mm) [12, 13]. Therefore, any attempt to transfer lightweight solutions from passenger cars has to consider such specific loading requirements of HDVs. Additionally, chassis parts for HDV have many holes for fastening and part assembly. Mechanical cutting and punching are used in the HDV industry because they allow high production rates and quick cost recovery for mechanical tools. Surface characteristics, such as heterogeneities formed during cold or hot rolling, oxidation pits and especially the defects generated during forming or shearing, strongly affect the fatigue resistance of high strength steel sheets (HSSs) [14–16].

Mechanical cutting of thick sheets is a severe forming operation, involving high loads. It results in surface defects and residual stresses along the sheared edge, which impair the fatigue resistance of AHSS grades [17–24]. Residual stresses have a more detrimental effect on fatigue performance than the surface roughness and the edge defects in AHSS [25, 26]. Aimed to reduce the surface roughness and the residual stresses in sheared thick sheets, surface treatments are typically applied. Before the painting operation, HDV chassis parts are blasted to clean the surface and ensure paint adhesion. Sand blasting (using round alumina or corundum particles) and shot blasting (using sharp-edge grits or round shots) are typically used to clean

FIGURE 1 | Example of the increase in transport efficiency by truck lightweighting.

surfaces. Blasting rounds the sheared edges, smooths the hole profile and introduces compressive residual stresses [15, 27–32]. Both effects are known to increase the fatigue resistance of sheared edges. The intensity of the residual stress field is proportional to the yield strength (YS), so the effect on the fatigue strength is higher when YS increases. For very high-strength materials, as press hardened steels, shot peening (using small spherical shots or beads) is a well-recognized process to increase the in-service performance of components subjected to severe cyclic loads or wear and corrosion conditions [29–32]. When optimized for material and thickness, shot peening has been shown to increase fatigue life by hardening the surface and inducing a field of deep and substantial compressive residual stresses [33].

Most HDV chassis parts are currently cold formed using microalloyed steels with a ferritic-pearlitic microstructure. Among the different AHSS grades, the Complex Phase (CP) steel family is a convincing solution for parts requiring a favorable combination of strength and fracture toughness. The microstructure of CP steels consists of a small amount of martensite and retained austenite dispersed in a fine matrix of bainite and ferrite [34, 35]. This microstructure balances the strength of the different microstructural constituents and has low internal stresses, resulting in a high fracture toughness [36]. As a result, CP steels are highly damage-tolerant, which means less sensitive to edge defects. Therefore, they are particularly suitable for load bearing components with sheared or punched edges, as chassis parts [8, 36, 37].

Press hardening of B steels is now widely used in the automotive industry to obtain very high-strength components, in the range of 1500 MPa, due to their martensitic microstructure [38]. The process allows forming complex part geometries thanks to the high sheet formability in the austenitic state. The technology is mature and widely implemented to manufacture BiW components for passenger cars, usually with thin sheets of 1–2 mm thickness. HDV's chassis parts require the use of thicker sheets, often more than 6 mm thick, to ensure high part stiffness. Press hardening of thick sheets is possible with only moderate adaptations of the technology. Full martensitic microstructures were demonstrated for 7 mm sheet using a conventional process with minimal adaptation [39, 40].

The high strength of the press-hardened condition makes the microstructure very sensitive to pre-existing defects [23, 26, 41–43]. In thin cold rolled 22MnB5 sheets (1–2 mm) the cracks in the Al-Si coating or the edge damage at punched holes trigger fatigue fracture [23, 42, 43]. Thick hot rolled 22MnB5 steels show some differences with thinner gauges. First, thick 22MnB5 steels are uncoated, so the surface is free from the cracks typically present in the Al-Si coating. Second, mechanical shearing or punching in as-quenched conditions is not industrially feasible in thick sheets due to the high forces developed in the cutting process [21]. Instead, laser cutting is the option to trim the part edges and introduce holes. Punching in the soft annealed state is not feasible, as holes deform during quenching. It is not allowed as it would compromise proper bolting. Although laser cutting may introduce surface defects, it has less impact on fatigue strength than mechanical cutting [19–22]. As mentioned before, all HDV parts are blasted after manufacturing. This process rounds edges and induces residual stresses that would effectively counterbalance the laser-induced edge damage. The very high YS of press hardened steels (higher than 1000 MPa) offers the possibility to increase fatigue strength through shot peening processes. Previous works reported an increase of about 15%–20% of fatigue strength in blasted 22MnB5 steel [44, 45]. Greater

improvements can be reached by shot peening. Sunderkötter et al. reported an increase of more than 30% in the fatigue strength at 10^5 cycles and more than 50% for the fatigue limit at 2×10^6 cycles) [31, 44]. The distinct effects at 10^5 and 10^6 cycles are well documented and stem from how surface hardening impacts each fatigue regime [46]. Therefore, press hardening is an interesting forming process to address lightweight construction of chassis parts for HDVs because it allows forming complex geometries using thick sheets with high fatigue strength after shot peening.

1.3 | Aim

This work aims to evaluate the feasibility of lightweighting HDV chassis components through a combined approach that integrates material and forming process selection with life cycle assessment (LCA). The study focuses on hot-rolled AHSS, including a CP grade, and press-hardened boron steel, assessing their mechanical suitability for chassis applications and the environmental impacts associated with the forming process used for thick sheets, i.e., cold forming and press hardening. By coupling performance requirements with comprehensive LCA, this research provides a holistic framework for selecting sustainable solutions that reduce chassis weight while minimizing environmental footprint. These solutions support energy-efficient vehicle operation and align with long-term decarbonization objectives for the HDV sector.

2 | Materials and Experimental Procedures

2.1 | Materials

Current chassis parts in HDVs are produced with hot-rolled steels with a thickness of around 10 mm using mild and high-strength low alloy (HSLA) steels. In this work, a S355 mild steel and a S500MC steel, an HSLA grade, are set as a reference for the lightweight potential of two AHSS grades, a CP steel (HR800CP) and a high-strength grade (S700MC), and a press-hardened 22MnB5 steel. The thickness of the tested specimens is 5 or 6 mm, except for the S355 steel, which is 3 mm (fatigue strength of thicker gauges is expected to be similar, only fracture toughness may decrease down to 202 kJ/m² due to the change of the stress state conditions [47]). The chemical composition and mechanical properties of these steels are shown in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

The S500MC steel exhibits a ferritic-pearlitic microstructure, such as the S355, but with a very fine dispersion of alloy carbides. The steel S700MC has a ferritic-bainitic microstructure. HR800CP shows a fine microstructure containing martensite and retained austenite islands within a ferritic-bainitic matrix, typical for the CP steels family. The 22MnB5 steel was uncoated and die quenched after austenitizing the sheet at 930°C for 330 s. The resulting microstructure was fully martensitic.

2.2 | Mechanical Characterization

Axial tensile tests were performed in a universal testing machine according to ISO 6892 standard. The tensile specimens were machined transverse to the rolling direction. Fracture toughness was assessed following the essential work of fracture methodology.

TABLE 1 | Chemical composition for the investigated steels in %weight (the balance is Fe).

Steel	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Al	Ti + Nb	Cr + Mo	B
S355	0.07	0.017	0.58	0.006	≤0.001	0.04	≤0.03	0.03	—
S500MC	0.07	0.022	0.79	0.007	≤0.001	0.04	≤0.03	0.03	—
S700MC	0.12	0.5	1.6	≤0.05	≤0.001	—	—	—	—
HR800CP	0.20	1.00	2.20	≤0.05	≤0.001	0.015–1.2	≤0.25	≤1.00	≤0.005
22MnB5	0.220–0.225	0.15–0.35	1.10–1.40	≤0.025	≤0.008	0.02	0.02–0.06	—	0.002–0.005

TABLE 2 | Tensile properties (yield strength (YS), tensile strength (UTS), and total elongation (TE)) measured at 90° with respect to the rolling direction. Fracture toughness is expressed in terms of the essential work of fracture (w_e).

Steel	YS, MPa	UTS, MPa	TE, %	w_e , kJ/m ²
S355 (3 mm)	464 ± 11	477 ± 15	58,4 ± 3,1	289 ± 12
S500MC (6 mm)	641 ± 8	651 ± 12	23,4 ± 2,2	367 ± 67
S700MC (6 mm)	863 ± 7	902 ± 14	18,9 ± 1,2	191 ± 15
HR800CP (5 mm)	785 ± 8	902 ± 10	18,3 ± 2,2	302 ± 60
22MnB5 (6 mm)	1028 ± 18	1561 ± 22	4,5 ± 1,5	38 ± 8

It is based on elastic-plastic fracture mechanics and has been successfully applied to characterize the fracture toughness of HSS sheets [48, 49]. The method estimates the essential work of fracture (w_e), which under certain circumstances may be considered as equivalent to the *J-integral* value and has been proved to effectively describe the fracture resistance of AHSS sheets [48]. The method relies on testing multiple precracked specimens with different ligament lengths up to fracture and measuring the energy required for the complete fracture of the specimen. The methodology is described in detail in the CWA 177932021 [49]. Single edge notched bending (SENB) specimens were used with dimensions of 120 x 28 x 6 mm. The value of w_e was evaluated in bending tests, following the procedure described in [40] and [50]. The results for tensile properties and fracture toughness are reported in Table 2

The fatigue resistance was experimentally obtained by constructing the stress versus number of cycles (SN) curve. Hourglass specimens were tested in a servo-hydraulic machine at a load ratio ($R = \sigma_{min} / \sigma_{max}$) of -1 . Truck chassis parts are dimensioned to resist 100.000 load cycles, so the fatigue strength at such a level (σ^{100k}) was considered in this work to select the steel to reduce weight and to design the demonstrator.

Fatigue specimens were prepared by mechanically shearing a rectangular plate of 170 x 25 mm. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 2. A cutting clearance, i.e. the distance between the punch

and the die, of 10% was used. After shearing, a sandblasting treatment was applied to replicate the shot blasting treatment performed in the industrial manufacturing of chassis parts to degrease and prepare the surface for the painting process. In this work, the sandblasting process was carried out with glass microspheres of 40 to 95 μm in diameter as abrasive media. For a batch of specimens, the trimmed edges were machined and polished to obtain the intrinsic fatigue resistance of the material. The 22MnB5 specimens were machined from die-quenched rectangular plates. For a specimen batch, the edges were polished, and for another batch, the specimens were shot peened.

2.3 | Demonstrator

A crossmember has been selected as a case study. Crossmember beams are positioned between the two long frame members or frame rails in trucks, see Figure 3. There are usually different designs of the crossmembers, depending on stiffness requirements and how much space is available due to parts like the drive shaft, gearbox, and exhaust system. If no parts interfere with the design of the crossmember, then the design can be quite simple (green part). The red part shows an example of maximum interference, where the design needs to be much more complicated to be able to transfer the same forces and torque. The forces the crossmember

FIGURE 2 | (a) Fatigue specimens with trimmed edges, colored in red. The dimensions are expressed in mm. (b) Rigid tools are designed to trim the fatigue specimens.

FIGURE 3 | (a) Crossmember used in case study. (b) Location of the crossmember in a truck. (c) Meshed beam. (d) Sketch of the loading case used to design the demonstrator.

needs to transfer arise when the two frame members move independently. Parts mounted on the outside of the frame members, such as the fuel tank and battery, are subjected to accelerations during normal truck operation, which expose the crossmember to torque. The stress levels acting on the crossmembers during normal truck use should be below the YS of the material. However, since these stresses are cyclic, there exists a notable risk of fatigue failure.

The most critical load case for a chassis is a lateral bending. It occurs on trucks with more than two axles during slow cornering, i.e. usually at road intersections and roundabouts. So, this was the load case selected in this work to dimension the demonstrator and show the lightweight potential of different steels. The design was done with finite element simulations of a linear displacement of the beam under lateral bending (x-direction in Figure 3d). The beam is modeled with solid elements of approximately 3 mm mesh size. A linear elastic material model is used for half of the beam, considering the symmetry of the component. A 150 mm long rigid part is added to the end of the beam, where a described displacement of 2.5 mm is added to one of the nodes (node 13 600 in Figure 3c). The back nodes of the beam are locked in all directions (marked in red in Figure 3c) to model the clamping of the beam. The simulation was used to determine the increase of strength needed in a 6 mm demonstrator to perform as a 9 mm part built with S355 steel.

2.4 | LCA Methodology

LCA stands as a well-established methodology to identify, describe, and evaluate the environmental aspects and possible effects of a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle. This involves creating a list of relevant inputs and outputs of a product system to assess its potential environmental impacts. It provides a comprehensive quantification of relevant emissions, resource consumption, associated environmental and health impacts, as well as resource depletion issues attributed to goods or services. The international standards ISO 14 040 [51] and ISO 14 044 [52] delineate the core framework and principles of LCA methodology, encompassing four interrelated phases: defining goal and scope, conducting inventory analysis, assessing impacts, and interpreting results. Additionally, the SPE-14 040–1475 standard [53], developed by the

CSA group, sets forth guidelines for performing comparative LCAs of automotive parts, which consider alterations in weight resulting from shifts in materials, manufacturing methods, or part geometry. The LCA process is structured into four phases, which will be detailed in subsequent sections: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory, life cycle impact assessment, and interpretation.

A cradle-to-grave approach has been adopted, as HDV lightweighting influences both the production and the use phase, and the latter dominates total environmental impacts due to the long operational lifetime and high annual mileage of HDVs. This study identifies three primary life cycle stages: The initial stage encompasses raw material extraction, manufacturing, and assembly; the second stage involves the operational phase of an electric vehicle (EV); and the final stage consists of end-of-life (EoL) considerations.

System boundaries encompass the production of the demonstrator, its operational phase, and EoL management. Accordingly, the primary inputs considered include energy and materials. This approach ensures a comprehensive assessment of the environmental and cost implications throughout the entire life cycle of the crossmember under study.

Within the raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly stage, the specific steps to produce a crossmember are depicted in Figure 4 for cold stamping and press hardening processes.

The functional unit is determined as the driving distance of 1 km. Although actual lifetime distance can vary significantly based on factors such as maintenance, usage patterns, and vehicle model, a lifetime driving distance of 1.000.000 km has been considered for the current assessment, in consistency with typical EU HDV cycles and with values used in recent HDV LCAs. Calculations were carried out using Simapro v9.5 software and the ecoinvent database v3.9 and the Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden (CML) Method.

3 | Experimental Results and Discussion

3.1 | Fatigue Results

Figure 5 presents the SN curves for the studied steels, with fatigue strength at 10^5 cycles listed in Table 3 and compared in Figure 5d. Results show a marked decrease in fatigue strength for high-strength steels (S700MC, HR800 CP) when the specimens are trimmed. The fatigue strength reduction was 38% for S700MC and 27% for HR800CP. In press hardening, no sheared specimens were tested, as explained in section 2.2, but reduction can be in the range of 40%–50%, following the results obtained in thin sheets [19]. Laser and waterjet cutting of 22MnB5 can be used to introduce holes and trim the edges, but they also introduce defects that reduce the fatigue strength by 10% to 30% [19, 45].

Blasting notably improves the fatigue resistance of sheared specimens, being larger for steel with high YS. In S355, the effect is almost negligible, because of the low YS, as reported in previous works [15, 32]. The increase in fatigue strength is more evident in higher strength steel, approaching it to the value for the polished specimens and surpassing it for S500MC and S700MC. Blasting increases the fatigue strength of sheared edges by 28% for S700MC and by 32% for HR800CP. Similar results were reported for HSSs [2528 303232]. In 22MnB5, the effect of blasting is lower, about a 20% increase. A value of σ^{100k} of 540 MPa is reported for blasted waterjet cut specimens, which had a σ^{100k} of 440 MPa

FIGURE 4 | (a) Cold forming route. (b) Press hardening process route.

[45]. This improvement is attributed to increased residual stresses from surface treatments, which intensify with treatment severity and higher YS [29–33]. In S355 and S500MC, the compressive residual stresses measured by XRD are around 340 and 440 MPa after sand blasting and shot blasting [16, 29]. In high-strength steel sheets, they are around -500 MPa [35].

Sand and shot blasting are surface cleaning processes. Apart from cleaning, they even round-trimmed edges and induced compressive residual stresses, which are not intended to enhance fatigue strength [32]. Shot peening, when optimized, induces a large and deep compressive residual field, reaching -800 to -1000 MPa in high strength steels ($YS > 1000$ MPa) [33]. Such residual stresses account for the improvement in fatigue strength of shot peened 22MnB5 steel, about 27% compared to polished surfaces. It can be even higher, up to 40%–50% when compared to laser or waterjet cut specimens [19, 45]. Previous works showed even higher values of σ^{100k} for press hardened steels, up to 630 MPa [27]. This variability in shot peening results shows that the process is highly dependent on shooting parameters. Therefore, it is recommended to optimize the processing parameters for each alloy and sheet thickness.

HR800CP shows a good combination of high YS, fracture toughness and σ^{100k} , making it a good candidate for lightweight construction of chassis parts. The higher fatigue performance of HR800CP compared to S700MC can be rationalized from a microstructural point of view. It is accepted that fine microstructures with low internal stresses, i.e. less difference in the hardness between the microstructural constituents, offer higher crack propagation resistance than mixtures of hard and soft phases. In this sense the CP-like microstructure of HR800CP with a mixture of fine martensite, bainite and ferrite exhibits higher crack propagation resistance than the dual ferritic–bainitic microstructures of S700MC. A recent work by Heshmati et al. points out the relevance of martensite at grain boundaries in DP-like microstructures, like S700MCPlus, that improves fatigue cracking resistance by inducing crack deflection [54]. The here studied standard S700MC grade does not show such intergranular martensite distribution.

Press hardened 22MnB5 offers a strong balance of YS and σ^{100k} , as shown in Table 3 and Figure 5. The measured fracture toughness is much lower compared to HR800CP (w_e of 38 kJ/m^2). Most of the published data of fracture toughness for structural steels is given by the critical stress intensity factor (K_{Ic}). For comparison purposes, the K_{Ic} can be estimated from the expression $K_{Ic} = (w_e E)^{1/2}$, where E is the Young's modulus, here considered as 220 GPa. The estimated K_{Ic} is $90 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$. It is not too low but lies at the lower end of the recommended range for structural use. However, blasting and specially shot peening reduce the defect sensitivity, because the process smooths the edges and lowers the roughness, which means shorter initial defects, and reduces the effective stress on edges. Therefore, fracture risk from processing defects remains low for most of the long-hauling trucks.

Nevertheless, it is advisable to evaluate the fracture toughness of thick press hardened specimens as it may vary with alloy composition and inclusion content. In addition, for trucks working under harsher conditions, like mining trucks, it is recommended to assess the fracture toughness at different temperatures. If higher toughness is needed, adding Nb and Mo to 22MnB5 steels doubles fracture toughness from 74 to 140 kJ/m^2 (in 4 mm plates) without impacting fatigue strength [55]. Alternatively, microstructural tailoring by adjusting quenching and tempering conditions can be used to enhance fracture toughness. Bainitic or tempered martensite microstructures can be developed by in-die controlled quench or laser postquenching treatment. Such soft zone techniques applied on passenger cars were demonstrated to be technically viable in 6 mm thick sheets, resulting in UTS above 900 MPa and fracture toughness, up to 130 kJ/m^2 (K_{Ic} of $170 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$) [40].

3.2 | Lightweight Design of an HDV's Crossmember

Crossmember beams are mostly subjected to bending loads. For this loading condition, the reduction of thickness of a plate from

the increase of the strength level can be estimated with Equation (1) that correlates thickness (t_1, t_2) with the strength level (σ_1, σ_2) [56]. σ_1 and σ_2 can refer to YS, UTS, or fatigue strength depending on the design criteria. Here, σ_1 and σ_2 represent the fatigue strength for a plate with a thickness t_1 and t_2 respectively.

$$t_2 = t_1 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2}} \quad (1)$$

Table 4 shows the thickness reduction due to the fatigue strength increase. As all proposed materials are steel grades with no significant difference in density, weight savings are directly linked to reduced thickness. The results shown in Table 4 give an estimation of the lightweight potential of each steel grade. HR800CP can reduce weight by 11%–21% weight reduction with respect to the current steel solution for crossmembers, as S355MC or S500MC respectively. Press hardened steels after sandblasting show similar results as HR800CP, a 15%–24% weight reduction.

FIGURE 5 | SN curves for the studied steels (a) S355; (b) S500MC; (c) S700MC; (d) HR800CP; (e) press hardened 22MnB5; and (f) comparison of the measured fatigue strength at 10^5 cycles (σ^{100k}) in terms of stress amplitude for different surface conditions.

FIGURE 5 | Continued.

The highest lightweight potential is for press hardened steels with a shot peening treatment, with a weight reduction of 25%–34% with respect to S355 and S500MC. Cold forming thick sheets, of about 6–7 mm, with a UTS higher than 800 MPa is difficult and industrially impractical, due to the high forming loads, the reduced formability and the pronounced springback. Press hardening is the only industrially viable process to produce very high-strength components with complex geometries at reduced thickness. It also offers a 14% weight reduction compared with

the highest strength steel solution manufactured by cold forming. A physical demonstrator with a 22MnB5 of 6 mm thickness was successfully built by press hardening and confirmed the process feasibility for crossmembers (Figure 6a).

Figure 6b shows the stress distribution in the 6 mm demonstrator during lateral bending. These results indicate the increased fatigue strength needed for the 6 mm part to match the performance of the 9 mm thick component, that is $\sigma_2/\sigma_1 = 2.2$. These results from modeling agree with the calculations from Equation (1).

TABLE 3 | Fatigue resistance at 100.000 cycles (σ^{100k}), in terms of stress amplitude, at $R = -1$ for different hot rolled AHSS grades and a press hardened 22MnB5 steel. The thickness is given in Table 2.

Steel	Polished edges, MPa	Sheared edges, MPa	Shear + sand blasting, MPa	Shear + shot peening, MPa
S355	273 ± 14	276 ± 14	285 ± 12	—
S500MC	325 ± 3	325 ± 10	362 ± 26	—
S700MC	482 ± 15 ±	306 ± 29	460 ± 21	—
HR800CP	469 ± 31	344 ± 21	455 ± 15	—
22MnB5	487 ± 29	—	—	619 ± 14

TABLE 4 | Thickness (t_2) calculated from Equation (1) considering σ_1 and σ_2 as the value of σ^{100k} for each pair of steels. The value for the condition 22MnB5 + blasting is extracted from reference 45.

Steel	σ^{100k} , MPa	t_2 compared to S355	t_2 compared to S500MC	t_2 compared to HR800CP
S355 + blasting	285	t_1	—	—
S500MC + blasting	362	0.88 t_1	t_1	—
HR800CP + blasting	455	0.79 t_1	0.89 t_1	t_1
22MnB5 + blasting	540 [45]	0.73 t_1	0.82 t_1	0.92 t_1
22MnB5 + shot peening	619	0.68 t_1	0.76 t_1	0.86 t_1

FIGURE 6 | (a) Picture of the physical demonstrator built with a 22MnB5 sheet of 6 mm thickness. (b) Stress distribution in the demonstrator (6 mm thick), showing how much the strength should be increased compared to a 9 mm thick demonstrator (ratio σ_2/σ_1).

The 6 mm demonstrator weighs 67% of the 9 mm version ($t_2/t_1 = 0.67$). According to Table 4 results the ratio between the fatigue strength of the demonstrator (6 mm, press hardened 22MnB5 with shot peening) and the S355 steel of the 9 mm original crossmember is 2.2 (619 MPa/285 MPa).

The weight savings shown in Table 4 are solely based on fatigue loading. Stiffness is also a part design requirement for HDV. Reducing sheet thickness lowers overall chassis stiffness. Calculation results indicate minimal impact on the affect adjacent crossmembers. Stiffness drops by about 2% and 6% in the 1st and the 3rd crossmembers. So overall chassis stiffness is not much affected. To offset this, geometrical changes are needed. This can be readily accomplished thanks to the high temperature formability and the design flexibility of press hardening. Therefore, to fully exploit the benefits of sheet downgauging with higher fatigue strength materials, geometric modifications are necessary. These may include the addition of geometrical stiffeners or altering the part geometry to compensate for the stiffness drop.

3.3 | Life Cycle Inventory

The life cycle inventory is a composition of experimental data, suppliers' information, and literature data. The inventory for all materials and energy consumed during the raw material extraction and manufacturing stage is provided in Table 5 for the cold stamping process and for press hardening.

All processes were modeled as explicit unit processes based on primary data obtained from the manufacturing facility, including energy consumption and material consumption. The upstream impacts of electricity and material production were represented using Ecoinvent datasets.

TABLE 5 | Life cycle inventory.

Process step	Inputs	Press hardening	Cold stamping	Cold stamping	Unit
		22MnB5	S355	HR800CP	
Blanking	22MnB5 steel	14,0	—	—	kg
	S355 steel	—	21,0	—	kg
	HR800 CP steel	—	—	16,3	kg
	Electricity Laser	0,747	0,022	0,017	kWh
	Electricity for transfer	0,060	1,120	0,870	kWh
	Cutting gas Oxygen	0,005	0,007	0,006	m ³
	Transport Rail	36,400	54,600	42,380	tkm
Furnace	Roller Furnace	1,330	—	—	kWh
	Electricity for transfer	0,060	—	—	kWh
Stamping	Stamping press	0,660	0,650	0,650	kWh
	Electricity for transfer	0,060	0,060	0,060	kWh
	Electricity for press compressors	—	—	1,014	kWh
Shot blasting	Shot blasting equipment	0,567	0,849	0,652	kWh
	Electricity for transfer	0,060	0,060	0,060	kWh
	Shot blasting abrasive	0,044	0,065	0,050	kg
Laser	Cutting gas Oxygen	0,005	0,007	0,006	m ³
	Electricity Laser	0,747	1,120	0,869	kWh
	Electricity for transfer	0,060	0,060	0,060	tkm
	Steel scrap	1,400	2,100	1,600	kg

The use phase for HDV in the truck sector is set to 1.000.000 km. Energy and fuel consumption for the BEV and ICE configurations are based on HDV-specific values obtained from the Scania (2024) long-haul LCA, which provides VECTO-derived consumption representative of European duty cycles [57]. The diesel HDV baseline is set at 23.56 L/100 km and the BEV at 1.14 kWh/km, consistent with typical HDV operation. For HEV and PHEV configurations, no harmonized HDV data exist in the literature. The values are depicted in Table 6. For HEV and PHEV configurations, no harmonized HDV data exists in the literature. Therefore, it has been derived based on the EEA Report [58] for LDV's considering electric powertrains as 100% for BEV, 30% for HEV and 50% for PHEV according to Tagliaferri et al. [59] and fuel and energy consumption based on the Scania report [57].

This approach represents a second-best approximation, applied only because robust HDV-specific LCIs for hybrid powertrains are not yet available. Importantly, since use-phase energy consumption scales proportionally for all material options, reasonable variations in HEV/PHEV efficiency do not affect the relative

ranking of the forming routes, which is mainly driven by mass differences and by the dominant contribution of the use phase.

EoL has been considered based on Europe statistics published by Eurostat [60] as 44% collected and treated for recycling. HDVs differ substantially from passenger cars in their EoL dynamics. In Europe, HDVs typically do not reach formal EoL pathways at the end of their first service life. Instead, they are frequently exported to markets outside the EU, where they remain in operation for several additional decades. Since these extended second-life uses occur outside regulated waste management systems, reliable data on the final disposal or recycling is not available. For this reason, a simplified and regionally representative recycling rate of 44% has been considered, based on Eurostat for EoL vehicles.

Moreover, ICEVs' 100% reliance on fossil fuels during the use stage results in global warming potential that is comparable to HEVs (1.776 kg of CO₂eq for press hardened 22MnB5, 2.075 kg of CO₂eq for cold stamped HR800 CP, and 2.658 kg of CO₂eq for cold stamped S355), whose partial electrification is offset

TABLE 6 | Energy and fuel consumption during the use stage for different vehicle powertrain technologies, for a 1.000.000 km driving distance. In parentheses the % of electric powertrain.

BEV	ICEV	HEV, 30%		PHEV, 50%	
Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle	Energy consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle	Fuel consumed during lifetime per kg of vehicle
111,76 kWh/kg	29 450 mL/kg	33,53 kWh/kg	20 615 mL/kg	55,88 kWh/kg	14 725 mL/kg

by limited electric range and increased vehicle weight. This trade-off is even more evident in PHEVs, where the heavier dual powertrain and frequent use of the combustion engine can lead to substantially higher emissions.

3.4 | Life Cycle Impact Assessment Results

In accordance with the mandatory elements stated in the ISO 14044:2006 standard [52], the selection of impact categories, category indicators and characterization models is mandatory for each and all LCA. For this study, the selected impact assessment method is CML-IA (baseline, version 3.08), including Abiotic depletion, Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), Global warming (GWP100a), Ozone layer depletion (ODP), Human toxicity, Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, Marine aquatic ecotoxicity, Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Photochemical oxidation, Acidification, and Eutrophication impact categories.

Findings are organized based on the predefined life cycle stages outlined in the goal and scope, offering a summary of the environmental performance from a broad perspective across each life cycle stage. The selected impact categories (climate change and abiotic depletion) were chosen due to their relevance to emissions and resource use, two key concerns in automotive component manufacturing. Moreover, results for the remaining impact categories follow a similar trend and can be consulted in Tables A1–A3 in the Appendix A. Results for climate change and abiotic depletion are presented in Tables 7 and 8 for the three options of vehicles and for the three different sheet manufacturing options for the crossmember, by cold stamping for S355 and HR800 CP, and press hardening with 22MnB5. Figure 7 presents the comparison results for the global warming potential of the three technologies to manufacture a crossmember. Figure 8 presents the results for abiotic depletion potential.

Results evidence that in the HDV the use stage significantly influences environmental impact results (Figure 7b). The contribution

of the use phase to the global warming effect is only dependent on the vehicle type and the electrification amount. It is lower (90%) for BEV and higher for PHEV (97%), while it is independent of the material used. The effect is more pronounced than in passenger cars for two reasons: the larger mileage for HDV (1 million kilometers) compared to passenger cars (180.000 km) and the larger weight of HDV. In the HDV the usage phase accounts for about 90% to 97% of the whole environmental impact for all the categories analyzed. In passenger cars, this contribution is in the range of 77% to 86% depending on the technology [61] and in light-duty vehicles can reach up to 80% [62]. The energy consumption and emissions during HDV operation are directly related to the weight and payload of the vehicle. Therefore, these results encourage weight savings through the development of high-strength materials and the corresponding forming processes.

The LCA performed on different steels and forming processes indicates that crossmembers manufactured through press hardening exhibit lower environmental impacts across all evaluated impact categories when compared to those produced using cold forming. Cold-stamped HR800CP performs better than S355, but remains less favorable than the press-hardened solution. Among the vehicle configurations, the BEV with a press-hardened crossmember achieves the lowest lifecycle impacts per km.

In all cases, environmental benefits range from 21% to 32%. For global warming potential, advantages are evident for press hardening processing in comparison with cold forming processes, with 21% lower impacts for cold forming of HR800CP and up to 32% for S355. This translates to savings of 249 kg CO₂eq, 881 kg CO₂eq, and 700 kg CO₂eq per km for BEV, HEV, and PHEV, respectively.

Press hardening shows the most favorable results because it enables the production of high-strength (1500 MPa) components with complex geometries, offering significant weight-saving potential, which is a crucial factor in reducing kg CO₂eq during the use phase.

TABLE 7 | Global warming for each manufacturing alternative expressed by life cycle stage and for the three vehicle options, in kg of CO₂eq.

Manufacturing	Raw material extraction, manufacturing & assembly	Use stage	Use stage	Use stage	EoL	BEV	HEV	PHEV
		BEV	HEV	PHEV				
Press Hardened 22MnB5	49,5	461	1.726	1.365	0,03	511	1.776	1.415
Cold stamped HR800CP	60,4	538	2.014	1.592	0,03	598	2.075	1.653
Cold stamped S355	67,9	692	2.590	2.047	0,04	760	2.658	2.115

TABLE 8 | Abiotic depletion for each manufacturing alternative expressed by life cycle stage and for the three vehicle options, (in kg Sb eq, which represents the depletion of nonrenewable resources, using antimony, Sb, as a reference).

Manufacturing	Raw material extraction, manufacturing & assembly	Use stage	Use stage	Use stage	EoL	BEV	HEV	PHEV
		BEV	HEV	PHEV				
Press Hardened 22MnB5	2,18E-04	1,01E-03	1,72E-02	1,25E-02	2,02E-08	1,22E-03	1,74E-02	1,28E-02
Cold stamped HR800CP	1,57E-04	1,17E-03	2,00E-02	1,46E-02	1,32E-09	1,33E-03	2,02E-02	1,48E-02
Cold stamped S355	5,08E-05	1,51E-03	2,57E-02	1,88E-02	2,24E-08	1,56E-03	2,58E-02	1,89E-02

FIGURE 7 | (a) Global warming comparison for different types of HDV: BEV, HEV and PHEV. Results are in kg of CO₂eq for a driving distance of 1 km considering all life cycle stages of a crossmember. (b) Impact of the use phase on global warming for the different vehicles and manufacturing processes (cold forming or press hardening).

FIGURE 8 | Abiotic depletion, in kg of Sb (antimuonium) equivalent, comparison for different types of HDV: BEV, HEV, and PHEV.

Road transport in Europe emits about 800 Mt of CO₂eq per year (2024). HDVs account for roughly 25% of these emissions. If each HDV reduces its life-cycle CO₂ emissions by about 67% through electrification and lightweighting, the potential reduction would be

around 134 Mt of CO₂eq per year. HR800CP steel shows high fatigue resistance for cold forming solutions. Among cold stamped AHSS grades, HR800CP offers a 13%–22% weight reduction compared to traditional steels, making it a viable alternative to press hardening.

The full set of midpoint impact categories is provided in the Tables in the Appendix for transparency. In the main text, we focus on Global Warming Potential and Abiotic Depletion, as these indicators are most directly linked to the objectives of this study: quantifying the climate benefits of lightweighting in HDVs and assessing the upstream raw material intensity associated with the different forming routes.

4 | Conclusions

This work underscores the potential of press hardening technology to address lightweighting action in HDV to contribute to the global objectives of reducing the carbon footprint of the transport sector. Through a detailed LCA and materials selection based on fatigue resistance, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- When selecting a material for an HDV chassis part, the fatigue resistance of sheared and blasted edges has to be considered. Blasting notably improves the fatigue resistance for steels with high YS, higher than about 800 MPa.
- HR800CP shows the highest fatigue resistance of sheared edges among the tested steels without surface treatments. It can reduce weight by 13% compared to microalloyed steels, increasing to 22% with blasting. Cold forming thick HR800CP sheets requires high loads and causes significant springback, which may limit their practical use for large parts.
- Press hardened 22MnB5 steel shows high fatigue resistance, but surface treatments as blasting or peening are necessary to avoid fatigue initiation from holes or edges. Shot peening delivers the highest fatigue resistance and offers over 30% weight savings compared to microalloyed steels.
- Sheet downgauging can reduce weight, but stiffness loss should also be addressed. In this work, the case study does not show much affection to chassis stiffness, no more than 6%, reduction. For widespread use of press hardening in HDV chassis parts, designs should include geometric stiffeners and/or local geometry variations.
- The use phase dominates environmental impacts, particularly due to the extended vehicle lifetime (1 000 000 km) for HDVs. For all assessed vehicle configurations, the use stage contributes between 90% and 97% of the total environmental impact across all vehicle categories.
- The large share of environmental impact arising from the use stage makes lightweighting a key strategy for reducing overall emissions. This underscores the critical importance of design decisions and material selection as essential drivers in minimizing life cycle environmental impact in the transport sector.
- Press hardening of thick sheets stands as the most convenient sheet forming route to produce fatigue dimensioned components for HDVs. It allows about 30% weight savings and offers higher environmental benefits, in the range of 21% to 32% than sheet cold forming.

Author Contributions

Daniel Casellas: conceptualization (lead), formal analysis (equal), funding acquisition (equal), investigation (lead), methodology (equal),

supervision (lead), validation (lead), writing – original draft (lead), writing – review & editing (lead). **Violeta Vargas-Parra:** data curation (lead), formal analysis (lead), funding acquisition (equal), investigation (equal), methodology (equal), supervision (lead), validation (lead), writing – original draft (lead), writing – review & editing (lead). **Sergi Parareda:** funding acquisition (equal), investigation (equal), methodology (equal), validation (supporting), writing – original draft (supporting), writing – review & editing (supporting). **Jose Jorge Espi-Gallart:** writing – review & editing (supporting). **Jaume Pujante:** writing – review & editing (equal). **Gustaf Gustafsson:** conceptualization (supporting), funding acquisition (supporting), investigation (equal), validation (supporting), writing – original draft (supporting), writing– review & editing (supporting). **Henrik Sieurin:** conceptualization (supporting), investigation (supporting), validation (supporting), writing – original draft (supporting), writing – review & editing (supporting). **David Frómata:** investigation (supporting), methodology (supporting), validation (supporting), writing – review & editing (supporting).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the LCA analysis are given in Tables A1, A2, and A3, in Appendix A. Any additional data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE A1 | LCA results for manufacturing a crossmember using a S355 steel, as a base solution.

Manufacturing	Raw material extraction, manufacturing & assembly	Use stage	Use stage	Use stage	EoL	BEV	HEV	PHEV
		BEV	HEV	PHEV				
Abiotic depletion	5,08E-05	1,51E-03	2,68E-02	9,44E-01	2,24E-08	1,56E-03	2,69E-02	9,44E-01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	6,40E + 02	8,21E + 03	3,48E + 04	1,16E + 06	4,99E-01	8,85E + 03	3,54E + 04	1,16E + 06
Global warming (GWP100a)	6,79E + 01	6,83E + 02	2,76E + 03	9,18E + 04	3,57E-02	7,51E + 02	2,83E + 03	9,19E + 04
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	1,03E-06	9,70E-06	4,31E-05	1,44E-03	5,19E-10	1,07E-05	4,41E-05	1,44E-03
Human toxicity	1,88E + 01	1,23E + 03	1,58E + 04	5,51E + 05	7,57E-02	1,25E + 03	1,58E + 04	5,51E + 05
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	2,24E + 01	5,24E + 02	3,13E + 03	1,07E + 05	2,19E + 00	5,48E + 02	3,16E + 03	1,07E + 05
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	3,99E + 04	1,35E + 06	6,54E + 06	2,20E + 08	6,55E + 02	1,39E + 06	6,58E + 06	2,20E + 08
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	6,65E-02	7,71E + 00	9,45E + 01	3,30E + 03	7,62E-05	7,77E + 00	9,46E + 01	3,30E + 03
Photochemical oxidation	2,05E-02	1,34E-01	4,82E-01	1,59E + 01	6,93E-06	1,54E-01	5,03E-01	1,59E + 01
Acidification	2,03E-01	2,95E + 00	8,82E + 00	2,85E + 02	2,21E-04	3,16E + 00	9,02E + 00	2,85E + 02
Eutrophication	7,57E-02	2,18E + 00	3,17E + 00	9,12E + 01	5,76E-05	2,25E + 00	3,25E + 00	9,13E + 01

TABLE A2 | LCA results for manufacturing a crossmember using a HR800 CP steel, solution with a 22% weight reduction potential according to Table 4.

Manufacturing	Raw material extraction, manufacturing & assembly	Use stage	Use stage	Use stage	EoL	BEV	HEV	PHEV
		BEV	HEV	PHEV				
Abiotic depletion	1,57E-04	1,18E-03	2,09E-02	7,34E-01	1,32E-09	1,33E-03	2,10E-02	7,34E-01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	5,65E + 02	6,39E + 03	2,70E + 04	9,01E + 05	4,16E-01	6,95E + 03	2,76E + 04	9,02E + 05
Global warming (GWP100a)	6,04E + 01	5,31E + 02	2,15E + 03	7,14E + 04	3,15E-02	5,92E + 02	2,21E + 03	7,15E + 04
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	8,04E-07	7,55E-06	3,35E-05	1,12E-03	4,01E-10	8,35E-06	3,43E-05	1,12E-03
Human toxicity	1,02E + 02	9,59E + 02	1,23E + 04	4,28E + 05	7,13E-02	1,06E + 03	1,24E + 04	4,28E + 05
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	3,47E + 01	4,07E + 02	2,44E + 03	8,30E + 04	2,18E + 00	4,44E + 02	2,47E + 03	8,30E + 04
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	8,19E + 04	1,05E + 06	5,08E + 06	1,71E + 08	6,47E + 02	1,13E + 06	5,17E + 06	1,71E + 08
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	9,78E-01	5,99E + 00	7,35E + 01	2,57E + 03	3,46E-05	6,97E + 00	7,45E + 01	2,57E + 03
Photochemical oxidation	1,81E-02	1,04E-01	3,75E-01	1,23E + 01	5,50E-06	1,22E-01	3,93E-01	1,24E + 01
Acidification	1,96E-01	2,30E + 00	6,86E + 00	2,22E + 02	2,02E-04	2,49E + 00	7,05E + 00	2,22E + 02
Eutrophication	7,53E-02	1,69E + 00	2,47E + 00	7,09E + 01	5,09E-05	1,77E + 00	2,54E + 00	7,10E + 01

TABLE A3 | LCA results for manufacturing a crossmember using a 22MnB5 press hardened steels, with a 33% weight reduction potential according to Table 4.

Manufacturing	Raw material extraction, manufacturing & assembly							
	Use stage BEV	Use stage HEV	Use stage PHEV	EoL	BEV	HEV	PHEV	
Abiotic depletion	2,18E-04	1,01E-03	1,79E-02	6,29E-01	2,02E-08	1,23E-03	1,81E-02	6,29E-01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	4,73E + 02	5,47E + 03	2,32E + 04	7,73E + 05	4,49E-01	5,95E + 03	2,37E + 04	7,73E + 05
Global warming (GWP100a)	4,95E + 01	4,55E + 02	1,84E + 03	6,12E + 04	3,21E-02	5,05E + 02	1,89E + 03	6,13E + 04
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	7,26E-07	6,47E-06	2,87E-05	9,60E-04	4,67E-10	7,20E-06	2,94E-05	9,61E-04
Human toxicity	2,85E + 01	8,22E + 02	1,05E + 04	3,67E + 05	6,82E-02	8,51E + 02	1,05E + 04	3,67E + 05
Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	1,77E + 01	3,49E + 02	2,09E + 03	7,11E + 04	1,97E + 00	3,69E + 02	2,11E + 03	7,11E + 04
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	3,60E + 04	9,00E + 05	4,36E + 06	1,47E + 08	5,90E + 02	9,36E + 05	4,39E + 06	1,47E + 08
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	4,97E-01	5,14E + 00	6,30E + 01	2,20E + 03	6,86E-05	5,63E + 00	6,35E + 01	2,20E + 03
Photochemical oxidation	1,46E-02	8,92E-02	3,21E-01	1,06E + 01	6,24E-06	1,04E-01	3,36E-01	1,06E + 01
Acidification	1,60E-01	1,97E + 00	5,88E + 00	1,90E + 02	1,99E-04	2,13E + 00	6,04E + 00	1,90E + 02
Eutrophication	6,03E-02	1,45E + 00	2,12E + 00	6,08E + 01	5,18E-05	1,51E + 00	2,18E + 00	6,09E + 01